

Inspiring Educators?

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With the emergence of education challenges in Indonesia today, the trending hashtags *#JanganJadiGuru* and *#JanganJadiDosen* on X (Twitter) have acquired traction due to insufficient salaries and low income throughout numerous Indonesian high schools and universities. This has resulted in a reduction in enthusiasm for teaching, as evidenced by comments on X. Furthermore, the gap between educators' requirements and compensation, along with an oppressive workload, has exacerbated these frustrations. The outrage resonates deeply on X, and as I consider my own future as an educator in the *Nusantara*, I can't help but think about these situations, hoping to contribute to students' intellectual growth and development.

As I continue my learning journey and watch the current trends in X's educational scene, notably the hashtags *#JanganJadiGuru* and *#JanganJadiDosen*, I am motivated to look deeper into the complexity of the educator's job. Giving without expecting anything in return is like the sun beaming on the planet indefinitely. This introspective trip encourages a deep consideration of the many obligations that come with being an educator. Let's look into each of these roles:

1. Teaching

Teaching is more than just transmitting knowledge; it is a sophisticated process that facilitates learning and fosters intellectual progress. Using constructivist theories of learning, educators must design meaningful learning experiences that engage students and enable them to construct their own understanding of the subject (Vygotsky & Cole, 1978). This entails using a variety of educational tactics customized to the various needs of students (Tomlinson, 2017). Furthermore, educators must foster a healthy classroom environment defined by mutual respect, collaboration, and curiosity (Brophy, 2006).

2. Researching

Scholarly research is vital for educators who want to keep current in their profession and contribute to the advancement of knowledge. Based on the principles of inquiry-based learning, research enables educators to investigate unresolved questions, test ideas, and develop new insights (Brew, 2017). Educators can improve their teaching techniques and make significant contributions to their field by using rigorous research methodologies and critically reviewing existing literature (Creswell, 2014).

3. Writing

Effective written communication is essential in academia because it allows for the spread of knowledge and intellectual debate (Birkenstein & Graff, 2018). Using academic writing standards, educators must improve their ability to construct clear, coherent, and evidence-based arguments (Walker & Kelly, 2017). Whether producing scholarly articles, research papers, or instructional materials, educators must follow accepted academic writing and citation patterns (APA, 2010).

4. Consulting

Educators frequently act as consultants, providing experience and direction to a variety of stakeholders both within and outside the educational setting. Based on educational leadership concepts, consulting entails working with students, coworkers, administrators, and community members to address educational difficulties and create positive change (Glickman *et al.*, 2001). Educators may promote cooperation, innovation, and continual improvement in educational practice by drawing on their experience and interpersonal skills.

5. Innovating

Innovation is critical for accelerating growth and fulfilling the changing demands of learners in the twenty-first century. To improve learning outcomes, educators must embrace evolving technology, pedagogical techniques, and instructional methodologies in accordance with educational innovation principles (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Educators can stimulate their students' creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills by cultivating an innovative culture (Wagner, 2010). Furthermore, educators must be willing to take chances, try out new ideas, and adapt their approach to changing educational situations (Fullan, 2015).

6. Administering

Administrative responsibilities are essential to the educator's function, necessitating strong organizational and management abilities (Glatthorn *et al.*, 2018). To maintain the efficient functioning of educational institutions, educators must monitor curriculum development, student assessment, program evaluation, and budget management, all of which are based on educational administration concepts. Educators can help students succeed and institutions achieve by properly managing resources and cultivating an accountability culture.

To put it simply, an educator's responsibility is multidimensional, requiring a diverse skill set and a dedication to lifelong learning. Educators who embrace these duties and responsibilities can have a significant impact on their students' lives while also contributing to the growth of knowledge in their profession. Ultimately, the trending hashtags #*JanganJadiGuru* and #*JanganJadiDosen* on X (Twitter) shed light on the severe difficulties that Indonesian educators confront, such as low pay and onerous workloads. As I evaluate my future as an educator in Indonesia, it is clear that the profession is more than just teaching. It also includes research, writing, consulting, innovation, and administration. Educators play a critical role in creating society's future, and by taking on these duties with resilience and a dedication to continuing learning, they may promote transformational change in education.

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